

A DAMAGE MICROMECHANICS MODEL OF A SMC-TYPE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

A micromechanical damage model of a SMC-type composite is developed and the results are compared with both mechanical and ultrasonics testings. Based on Mori and Tanaka's theory, the model predicts the stiffness tensor of the material damaged or not, as well as the stress strain curve and the damage mechanisms, until the point of failure.

Keywords : Micromechanics, Damage, Composite, Ultrasonics.

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE MATERIAL

The material studied here is a SMC-type composite, whose plates have been manufactured by a research laboratory of the Regie Renault. The SMC is a three-phase composite material composed of a matrix of polyester resin, mineral charges and a reinforcement of 2,5 cm long glassfibers. The fibers are randomly orientated and therefore the final material is theoretically transversely isotropic (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 : Structure of SMC

The fibers are put together in the form of bundles, that are more or less aligned in the plane of the material. The presence of porosities and the heterogeneity of this material can be noted. The matrix, charged with CaCO₃ and containing microscopic porosities has different characteristics from that of the polyester solely. The mechanical characteristics of its constituents are described in the table 1 :

Matrix Modulus Em	7 GPa	Fiber Volume Fraction f	0,32
Matrix Poisson's ratio ν_m	0,35	Fiber Massic Fraction	0,42
Fiber Modulus Ef	73 Gpa	Matrix strength Rm	55 MPa
Fiber Poisson's ratio ν_f	0,28	Fiber strength Rf	1500 MPa

Table 1 : Mechanical characteristics

2. ELASTIC CHARACTERISTICS

2.1. Determination by ultrasonics measurements

An ultrasonics immersion device is used to determine the stiffness tensor of anisotropic materials. It is sought to measure the wave propagation time through the sample (1). To this end, an ultrasonic testing machine is used : it is composed of 2 translators, for emission and reception, between which a sample, whose elastic constants are to be measured, is inserted. The whole is put in a tank with a thermostat, that allows to keep the water temperature constant, which is important to get accurate results.

A micro-computer pilotes the displacements, controls the emission and reception of ultrasonic waves, digitizes the signal given by specific cards, makes out optimization calculations and plots slowness curves and finally provides different elastic constants of the material (Fig. 2). (2)

Figure 2 : Schematized ultrasonics testing machine used to characterize materials.

2.2. Theoretical determination based on the Mori-Tanaka's model

The model used to determine the elastic characteristics of the material is Mori-Tanaka's, (3 ; 4).

This material is characterized by a family of reinforcements Ω_i , of orientation θ_i and of relative volume fraction f_i ($\sum f_i=1$) (infinitely long ellipsoids that are distributed between 0 and 180 degrees in the plate plane and embedded in the matrix).

The basic equations are briefly mentioned. The stiffness tensor C is defined by :

$$(1) \quad C = C_m [I + f Q (I + N)^{-1}]^{-1}$$

$$(2) \quad N = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\Omega_i} (S_i - I) Q_i dv$$

$$(3) \quad f Q = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{\Omega_i} Q_i dV$$

$$(4) \quad Q_i = [(C_m - C_f) (S_i - I) - C_f]^{-1} (C_m - C_f)$$

where C_m is the stiffness tensor of the polyester resin, C_f that of fiberglass reinforcements, I the Identity and finally S_i denotes the Eshelby's tensor of reinforcement Ω_i .

2.3. Results

The axes 2 and 3 represent the axes of the plate isotropy and 1 is the normal vector (figure 3).

Figure 3 : Axes used

	C33	C11	C13	C55	C44	
Ultrasonic	23,6	15,6	6,6	4,7	6,4	GPa
Computed	24,5	16,9	8,36	4,33	6,95	GPa

Table 2 : Elastic characteristics of the non-damaged material

A good agreement of ultrasonic experiments with the model can be noted (table 2). The material data are shown in the table 1.

3. INFLUENCE OF CONSTITUENTS ON THE ELASTIC CHARACTERISTICS

3.1. Local measurement of the fibers orientation distribution

The material properties are essentially linked to the orientation and volume fraction of fibers (5). Experimental works of C. L. Tucker and col. (6) have shown that the flow of the fiber-matrix mixture in the course of elaboration can change, in some cases, the fibers orientation. These

reorientated fibers are determined by a tight coupling between ultrasonic measurements and the micromechanical approach described previously.

Different tests have been performed on each sample (turning, after each measurement, the specimen of 10° from 0° to 90°) in order to detect the fibers orientation on the whole plate. It is considered that, for a same volume percentage of reinforcement, the increase of the modulus in a direction, results directly from a main orientation of fibers in this same direction.

An exhaustive study of the sample allows to locate a peak at 15 degrees where the maximum gap is :

$$\frac{(C_{(15)} - C_{(-74)})}{C_{(-74)}} = 5,8\%$$

3.2. Modelisation of local anisotropy

The Mori-Tanaka's model is now used to determine the distributed orientation of fibers in the plate plane that gives the evolution of C11 measured previously.

We introduce the local anisotropy into the model, with a non-constant orientation distribution for the families of reinforcements Ω_i in each direction in plane 2-3. We have introduced the following sinusoidal orientation distribution of reinforcements :

$$f_i = f_0 \cdot (1 + f^* \cdot \cos(2 \cdot \theta_i))$$

With the help of our homogeneization model, we have tried to find out the fibers repartition likely to generate exactly this anisotropy of 5,8 %.

In entering $f^* = 0,14$, we obtain this gap : there are 14 % more fibers than the average in the direction of 15° and 14 % less in the perpendicular direction (75°).

This result is of particular interest since it confirms the possibility of finding, after moulding and locally, the distribution of microstructural parameters, as the distribution of fibers orientation.

4. THE DAMAGE MECHANICS :

4.1. Load curve

Through various observations (Scanning Electronic Microscope, Replicas and Optical Microscopy), the different steps of damage behavior have been identified in the course of loading (7).

Figure 4 : Tensile curve of the SMC-R42

According to this study, the behavior curve shown in figure 4 can be divided into different zones :

- . The linear zone AB relative to the elastic stage of its behavior

- . The zone BC during which an important stage of the damage mechanics occurs. The damage process initiates in the proximity of the point B and is produced by a decohesion mechanism at the interface of fibers desoriented with respect to the loading axis. Microcracks occur in the matrix confined inside the bundle.

- . Between C and D, the decohesion of fibers progresses quickly and the matrix crack density increases.

The failure occurs after the point D, located on the curve (Fig. 4). We have observed on the failure features, a shear mechanism at the fiber-matrix interface.

4.2. Ultrasonic damage measurements

The decreased ultrasonic velocities in the material results, during the damage process, from the emergence of new surfaces (crackings, decohesions), which make the material less rigid and leads to a slower wave propagation (8).

In order to avoid the closing of crackings, we have designed a device, which allows us to keep the sample in a tension state during ultrasonic measurements. Measurements have been performed in the 2 planes, one parallel to and the other perpendicular to the load axis. The results are shown in fig. 9.

4.3. Damage modeling

Damage criteria

The damage modeling is based on the micromechanical approach presented previously and three damage criteria are locally introduced (fig. 5).

* Interface failure by debonding or slipping:

The observed damage mechanisms show that the failure occurs at the interface between the matrix and the fiber. We consider therefore the interface as an adhesive with a maximum normal stress as $\sigma_m = R_i$ (tensile resistance of the interphase) and a maximum tangential stress $\tau_m = R_i/2$. The stress vector at the interface can be calculated thanks to the continuity conditions of the interface.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sigma_{ij}^{int} = \sum_{ij} + \sigma_{ij} \\ \sigma = (1 - f) C_m (S - I) e^* \end{array} \right.$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sigma_{ij}^{ext} = \sigma_{ij}^{int} + C_{ijkl} \gamma_{kl} \\ \gamma_{kl} = \{ - C_{pqmn} e_{mn}^* M_{kp} n_q n_l + e_{kl}^* \} \\ \text{with } M_{kp} = 1/\mu_m \{ \delta_{kp} - n_k n_p / [2 (1 - \nu_m)] \} \end{array} \right.$$

* Fibers failure:

Since the stress tensor $\sum + \sigma_i$ is known (eq. 6,7 and 8) in each reinforcement Ω_i , we can derive the maximum tensile principal stress (Lamé's criterion) σ_{p1} , that is to be compared with the failure stress of reinforcements R_f .

(6) $\sigma_i = C_m (\bar{E} + (S_i - I)) Q_i (E_o + \bar{E})$

(7) $\bar{E} = - (I + N)^{-1} N E_o$

(8) $E_o = C_m^{-1} \sum$

Figure 5 : Damage criteria

On figure 6, we can visualize the level reached by these three criteria to their maximum (here on a tensile test).

Figure 6 : Levels reached by each damage criterion.

Modeling of the damaged material:

As mentioned earlier, the stress tensor of first damage can be calculated, from the applied tensor Σ . The next step consists in modeling this damaged material.

The method used has been to replace the debonded fiber by matrix. This approximation is relatively justified by the fact that "pull-out" tests on fibers generate slipping stresses close to . Then for the reinforcement Ω_i , this is equivalent to put down the following equation : $C_f=C_m$ or $Q_i=0$ (eq. 4). We homogenize the new composite obtained. Then we obtain the new applied stress tensor, which allows to reach the second damage state as well as the corresponding mechanism. The failure occurs when all the fibers are debonded. The tensile simulation on a SMC-composite predicts the stress level as well as the angle θ_i of the debonded family of reinforcements with respect to the tensile direction.

It is noticed in figure 9 that decohesions first occur at around the fibers orientation of 45° with respect to the load direction (section OA), then when fibers are close to 90° (section AB). Finally the angle θ progressively decreases until 0° (section BD). The damage process corresponds to the interface slipping (section OC) and the fibers failure when the latter are close to the load axis (section CD). Ultimately, then, as long as the fibers at 90° are not debonded (section AB), the tensile stress is almost stationary : it concerns a failure process.

Figure 7 : Evolution of the angle of decohesion and stress applied during a tensile testing.

4.4. Results

As expected, the model predicts stresses that are weaker than experimental data (damaged reinforcements being replaced by matrix). However, the knee-point as well as the failure stress can be rather exactly anticipated (Fig 8).

Figure 8 : Theoretical and experimental tensile curves

Ultrasonics measurements also allow to compare the evolution of the stiffness tensor during the damage process. C_{ij} represent the stiffness values of the damaged material (Fig. 9).

Figure 9 : Evolution of the stiffness tensor with the applied strain. ● : experimental ; O : theoretical

We got a good agreement for the prediction of the damage initiation, but the evolution of the predicted stiffness parameters with the applied strain, is too strong. This is due to the fact that the behavior of a decohered fiber is stiffer than the matrix alone. The second remark concerns the ultrasonic measurement. The resin is viscoelastic, so the Young modulus measured by this dynamic wave is higher than the one determined by classical tensile test and used for the modeling.

5. CONCLUSION

In order to get better information on the influence of the microstructure of a composite on its mechanical properties, we coupled ultrasonic measurements to a micro-macro model (Tanaka and Mori). We obtained the distribution of fibers orientation with a non-destructive way. The damage behavior has been simulated by replacing the decohered fiber by matrix which leads to a behavior a little bit too soft. But the fact to introduce three local damage criteria leads to a behavior law of the damaged materials which is very close to the damage mechanisms and has a physical meaning. This model also allows to predict the type of damage mechanisms as a function of the external load and the microstructure parameters.

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